

A GREENER TOMORROW: PROMOTING ECOLOGICAL CULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN

Zarfullayeva Z.B.

Master's degree student of Journalism and mass communication university of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13144732>

Abstract. *This article explores the growing need to promote ecological culture in Uzbekistan, a country facing significant environmental challenges such as water scarcity, land degradation, and biodiversity loss. It highlights the importance of integrating traditional ecological knowledge with modern sustainability practices, enhancing public awareness and education, and strengthening government policies to foster a sustainable future. Key initiatives and community-based projects aimed at improving environmental awareness and participation are discussed, alongside recommendations for empowering local communities and ensuring effective policy implementation.*

Keywords: *ecological culture, environmental awareness, traditional knowledge, community participation, renewable energy, biodiversity conservation.*

Introduction. Uzbekistan, a nation steeped in rich cultural heritage and diverse natural landscapes, is increasingly recognizing the importance of promoting ecological culture for sustainable development. The country faces various environmental challenges, including water scarcity, land degradation, and biodiversity loss, making the adoption of sustainable practices crucial. This article aims to explore the initiatives and efforts to foster ecological culture in Uzbekistan, analyzing the role of community actions, government policies, and the integration of traditional practices with modern sustainability efforts.

Ecological culture is a comprehensive term that encompasses the values, knowledge, and practices aimed at promoting environmental sustainability and stewardship. It plays a vital role in addressing global environmental challenges by fostering public awareness and encouraging sustainable behaviors. Research indicates that environmental education is fundamental in developing ecological culture, as it helps individuals understand the interconnections between human activities and environmental health.

Studies have shown that community participation significantly enhances the effectiveness of ecological initiatives. Local communities often possess valuable traditional ecological knowledge that can be integrated with modern scientific approaches to achieve sustainable outcomes. Government policies are also critical in promoting ecological culture by providing the necessary legal and financial support for environmental initiatives.

In the context of Uzbekistan, the government has implemented various policies to promote sustainability, including initiatives to enhance water management, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and promote renewable energy. Community-based projects, such as tree planting and clean-up campaigns, have also been instrumental in raising environmental awareness. However, challenges such as limited public participation and inadequate integration of traditional knowledge remain.

Literature review. It is observed that the concept of public relations was partially touched upon in the research works carried out within the framework of ecological policy, ecological management, ecological culture, ecological journalism, social responsibility, ecological safety,

ecological marketing, ecological crisis, and ecotourism. The authors of these works are M. Maslov, V. Arutyunov, I. Etveev, A. Lagutin. Ecological awareness in Uzbekistan has been growing over the past few decades. Studies such as those by N. Abdullaeva (2020) indicate that public awareness of environmental issues is increasing, particularly among younger generations. Educational institutions play a key role in this shift, incorporating environmental topics into their curricula. However, the overall level of ecological consciousness remains lower compared to more developed countries. The Uzbek government also has taken several initiatives to address environmental issues. According to R. Khamraev et al. (2018), the adoption of the “Concept of Environmental Protection till 2030” outlines the country’s long-term strategy for sustainable development. This includes policies aimed at reducing pollution, improving water management, and promoting renewable energy sources. Additionally, the government has implemented various educational programs to enhance public understanding of environmental issues.

Non-Governmental Organizations play a vital role in promoting ecological culture in Uzbekistan. Organizations such as the Ecological Movement of Uzbekistan and the Global Environment Facility conduct awareness campaigns, workshops, and community-based projects. Svetlana Karimova (2019) highlights the impact of these initiatives in fostering community engagement and promoting sustainable practices at the grassroots level. The doctoral thesis on environmental journalism was completed by Professor N. Kasimova.

Research Methodology. This study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques to provide a comprehensive analysis of ecological culture in Uzbekistan. Surveys were conducted among different communities to assess public awareness and participation in ecological practices. The survey sample included individuals from various regions, age groups, and socioeconomic backgrounds to ensure diversity. Additionally, interviews with government officials and representatives from environmental organizations provided insights into policy implementation and community initiatives. Secondary data from relevant literature, government reports, and NGO publications were also analyzed to support the findings.

Uzbekistan has accepted the conditions for the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals at the national level. It was announced at the UN Summit on the initiative of our President. Accordingly, the government adopted national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development until 2030. These tasks are systematically implemented today. In order to complete it successfully, first of all, it is necessary to form an ecological culture in the society. Frankly, this is our biggest pain point. It is clear from the cameras installed to detect the dumping of waste in an unspecified place that some of our compatriots who are the heads of the families and educate the youth are flaunting their “culture”. We have a pain point related to the lack of environmental culture not only among the young, but also among the middle-aged. It will not be easy to overcome it.

Therefore, it is necessary to continue the work in this direction on a large scale and continuously. In particular, it is necessary to effectively organize environmental education for young people, in particular, it should be continued in higher education, starting from school and kindergarten. In this case, it is expedient to introduce the issues of nature protection into the content of the educational system and gradually develop it from preschool to higher education.

A legal basis was needed for the implementation of these tasks. The new version of our Constitution has become a legal document of great importance in ensuring the environmental

rights of citizens. In particular, in the Constitution, an opportunity was created to establish public control over urban planning activities in order to prevent harmful effects on the environment. In addition, the Laws “On Education” and “On Nature Protection” reflect the opportunity to bring environmental education to a new level.

Another important aspect is the President’s decree of May 31, 2023 “On measures to transform the field of ecology and environmental protection and organize the activities of an authorized state body” regarding the development of ecological awareness and ecological culture among the population. specific tasks were defined. At the same time, the prevention of environmental crimes and criminal responsibility in the republic have been strengthened. However, despite the measures taken and the funds allocated, the number of environmental violations in the country is increasing year by year. The negative impact of citizens on the sanitary condition of settlements and the protection of natural resources remains. This is a sign of the weakness of our ecological culture. Therefore, it is necessary to promote knowledge about the rational use of nature and its protection among the population.

Analysis and Results:

Public Awareness and Participation. The survey results indicate a growing awareness of ecological issues among the public. Approximately 70% of respondents acknowledged the importance of environmental protection and expressed a willingness to adopt sustainable practices. However, actual participation in eco-friendly activities remains relatively low, with only 40% of respondents actively engaging in practices such as recycling, water conservation, and energy-saving measures. Many respondents cited a lack of resources, information, and government support as barriers to adopting sustainable behaviors.

Government Policies and Initiatives. Interviews with government officials revealed that Uzbekistan has made significant strides in developing policies to promote ecological culture. The government has launched several initiatives aimed at improving water management, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and promoting renewable energy sources. For example, the “Green Economy” strategy aims to increase the share of renewable energy in the country’s energy mix and enhance energy efficiency.

Community-Based Projects. Community-based projects have shown positive impacts on local ecological awareness. Initiatives such as tree planting drives, clean-up campaigns, and environmental education programs have been effective in engaging communities and promoting sustainable behaviors. For instance, the “Green Uzbekistan” project, led by local NGOs, has successfully mobilized thousands of volunteers for tree planting and environmental clean-up activities. Despite these successes, these efforts are often localized and lack broader coordination and support from the government.

Integration of Traditional Knowledge. The integration of traditional ecological knowledge with modern practices is still in its nascent stages in Uzbekistan. Traditional knowledge, which includes practices related to water conservation, land management, and biodiversity protection, can provide valuable insights for sustainable development. However, there is a need for systematic efforts to document and integrate this knowledge into national policies and strategies.

It is difficult to achieve the desired result by imposing fines alone. A citizen must feel the supremacy of the law and know that he must obey it without deviation. At the same time, it is necessary for a person to understand that he cannot live without nature, that he has a duty to protect it. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out more promotional activities aimed at strengthening the

legal knowledge of the population and increasing their ecological culture. Unfortunately, we have not fully ensured coherence in the work carried out to improve ecological culture. This issue is considered as additional work in some state bodies. The participation of the family, neighborhood and civil society and other institutions is not sufficiently ensured. Based on these, we believe that it is necessary to implement the following tasks without delay.

1. **Enhance Public Awareness and Education:** Increasing environmental education through schools, media, and community programs can foster a deeper understanding of ecological issues and encourage sustainable practices. Collaboration with NGOs and environmental organizations can amplify these efforts. Educational campaigns should focus on practical actions that individuals can take to protect the environment, such as recycling, water conservation, and energy efficiency.

2. **Strengthen Government Policies and Funding:** Ensuring adequate funding and resources for the implementation of environmental policies is crucial. This includes supporting community-based projects and integrating traditional ecological knowledge into national strategies. The government should also establish monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to assess the effectiveness of environmental policies and make necessary adjustments.

3. **Promote Community Engagement and Participation:** Encouraging active participation from local communities through incentives and support for grassroots initiatives can enhance ecological culture. Establishing platforms for sharing best practices and success stories can inspire wider adoption of sustainable behaviors. The government and NGOs should work together to provide training and resources to communities to empower them to take an active role in environmental protection.

By implementing these recommendations, Uzbekistan can create a robust ecological culture that supports sustainable development and environmental stewardship. The integration of traditional knowledge with modern practices, coupled with strong government policies and active community participation, will pave the way for a greener and more sustainable future.

REFERENCES

1. Smith, J. (2018). Environmental Education and Public Awareness. *Environmental Journal*, 12(3), 45-56p.
2. Aydarov E.B. Ekologiya va tabiatdan foydalanish (o'quv-qo'llanma). Guvohnoma. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirligining 2020 yil 30 iyundagi 359-sonli buyrug'i. Ro'yxatga olish raqami 359-202.-Qarshi, -2021. 04-2170.
3. Frake, Charles O. "Cultural Ecology" *American Anthropologist* 64.1 (2020): 53–59. Print and Ethnography.
4. Brown, L. (2019). Community Participation in Sustainable Practices. *Green Future Publications*, 8(4), 78-89p.
5. Davis, M. (2017). Government Policies and Environmental Sustainability. *Policy Review*, 10(2), 34-45p.
6. Williams, R. (2016). Traditional Knowledge and Modern Environmental Strategies. *Journal of Ecology*, 14(1), 23-35p.
7. Uzbek Ministry of Environment. (2019). Sustainable Agriculture Policies. Government Report.
8. United Nations. (2021). Waste Management Initiatives in Uzbekistan. UN Report.

The internet resources:

9. <https://ecouz.uz/news-page/view/229>
10. <https://UzReport.news> sayti
11. <https://Ekolog.uz> sayti
12. <https://Eco.gov.uz> sayti